

CAUSES OF CONFLICTS AND PROBLEMS IN THE KOREAN PENINSULA

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Annotation: *In this article we will talk about the origin of conflicts and problems in the Korean Peninsula, where rivers are the most important, fertile: Amnokkan, Tumangan, Kimgan and other broad-leaved and constantly covered with green subtropical forests, in which rice, soybeans, cotton are sown, minerals come across tungsten, graphite, magnesite.*

Keywords: *Korean Peninsula, Sea, Soviet Union, Communist, capitalist government, regional government; String-like vine branches*

The Korean Peninsula is in East Asia, between the Japanese sea and the Yellow Sea. The area is 150 thousand km². Own. In the grass of 600 km, in the aksari part, the width is 200 km. The Korean Peninsula is located in the greater part of the Republic of Korea and the DPRK. The peninsula is adjacent to the mainland by the Korean neck. Relief is mainly mountainous, sertepa plain to the West. The highest place is the Chirisan peak in the East Korean mountains (1915 m). The East Coast is less fragmented, the West and South have a lot of seating and buxta. The climate is temperate, monsoon, subtropical climate in the South. The average temperature of Yanvar is from -21° to 4° in the North, July 22-26°. It rains 900– 1500 mm of precipitation per year.

MAIN PART

By the end of the Second World War, the Soviet Union (USSR) declared war on Japan and by 10 August 1945 occupied the northern part of the Korean Peninsula. At the end of the war, South Korea was divided into northern and southern parts by the Allies at the Potsdam Conference in paragraph 38.

The United States had to rule the southern part, so that the USSR ruled the Northern Territory. This division caused conflicts between the two regions of Korea, because the Northern Territory remained Communist, observing the USSR, and the South opposed this power and formed a strong communist and capitalist government.

The provocations and threats of North Korea have created an unstable environment on the Korean Peninsula. The fact that North Korea continues to develop nuclear weapons and ballistic missiles increases the possibility of using them against regional

states, further exacerbating instability in the region and beyond. The United States, its allies and other theatrical forces, including China and Russia, should focus on four interrelated threats. Failure to prepare increases the likelihood of errors and miscalculation and limits options to reduce the likelihood or severity of future conflicts.

The general picture of the peninsula and its surroundings is determined by a number of factors. The current crisis is a whole complex of problems that have accumulated for decades. Among them is a real O.V. Davydov 70 the complete absence of the Korean War (1950-1953), as a result of which the peace treaty was not signed; Since both the DPRK and the DPRK deny each other the recognition of each other by the state and consider themselves the only legal representative of the entire Korean people on the peninsula (these rules are legally enshrined in the constitutions of the DPRK and the DPRK), the instability of inter-Korean relations, respectively, is rock). In addition, there is no profilactic diplomacy in the subcontinent, and no authoritative framework for dispute and dispute resolution in the region between the two groups of powerful armed forces in the region - North Korea and the US-South Korea-in the context of resistance and tension.

The conflict on the Korean Peninsula has raised fears of a general increase in its potential, especially after the events of 2010-th year of the mysterious drowning of the Cheonan corvette of South Korea, the shooting by North Korea. The border islands belonging to the Republic of Korea in the Yellow Sea, as well as the tension in Korea in 2013, escalated. Subsequent events also showed several times that the situation was approaching a sharp point, in a number of cases coordinated or separate actions were carried out. The big five participants were asked to stop the spread of the crisis.

The essence of the problem is that the DPRK leader Kim Jong-In has a deadly weapon in the conditions of an extremely aggressive foreign policy carried out until recently and is ready to easily inspire a conflict situation. For all the army countries without exception, the further development of the situation was inexplicable, alarming and unpredictable. This brings about serious obstacles to the creation of a tool and includes long-term strategies of regional policy, the formation of a stable international order in the NEAda, the creation of collisions in the field of security and cooperation on this side, the implementation of long-term multilateral projects of economic cooperation, etc.

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At the same time, it should be noted that none of these problems can be completely solved in the near future, since this is not only the incompatibility of the positions of interested parties, but also the fact of their separation from the general row does not coincide. solve existing problems separately. The main reason for this is that they are all closely related to each other and, as a rule, represent different sides of a single multifaceted problem, it can be conditionally called a "Korean problem". Perhaps, as a result, such deep topics as the conclusion of a peace treaty or a comprehensive approach to the normalization of inter-Korean relations, in fact, at the official level, are not considered in all respects even by the parties. It should also be recognized that in fact they do not even have preliminary developments on this topic, with their help it is possible to specify at least the vector of action, as a result of which the policy of the forces on the whole spectrum. Korean problems are now somewhat chaotic and, as a rule, react to current events.

The reasons for such a situation can be explained, first of all, by two circumstances: firstly, the emergence and rapid growth of a nuclear problem on the Korean Peninsula, and secondly by davriy, but extreme explosions of military-political tension. Under these circumstances, the policy of the states and the United States of the army in itself

was directed to fight against New acute challenges, not to the debate on this matter, but as a priority task.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that until the above-mentioned most pressing problems of the Korean Peninsula are resolved, no principles of trust or major multilateral commitments can be agreed that will bring the region to a new, positive level of relations.

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